

Molecular Pharmacology: Molecular determinants of the differential modulation of Ca_v1.2 and Ca_v1.3 by nifedipine and FPL64176

Yuchen Wang, Shiqi Tang, Kyle E. Harvey, Amy E. Salyer, T. August Li, Emily K. Rantz, Markus A. Lill, and Gregory H. Hockerman

A

B

Supplemental Figure 1. Differential Block of Ca_v1.2 and Ca_v1.3 by structurally distinct dihydropyridines- **A)** Chemical structures of nifedipine, amlodipine, isradipine, and azelnidipine. **B)** Block of Ca_v1.2 and Ca_v1.3 by two concentrations of each of the dihydropyridine drugs shown in A. Concentrations are given in μM. Note that each drug is significantly more potent in blocking Ca_v1.2 compared to Ca_v1.3. Amlodipine (1 μM: *P* < 0.05)(*N* = 4) Azelnidipine (1 μM: *P* < 0.05)(*N* = 5) Isradipine (50 nM; *P* < 0.01)(*N* = 5) Nifedipine (100 nM: *P* < 0.001)(*N* = 4) (1 μM: *P* < 0.001)(*N* = 4)

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Supplemental Figure 2. Block of $Ca_v1.3$, $Ca_v1.3/DHPi$, and $Ca_v1.3+$ by the benzothiazepine diltiazem- **A)** Example current traces showing dose-dependent block of current conducted by $Ca_v1.3$ and $Ca_v1.3/DHPi$ by diltiazem. **B)** Fraction of current blocked by 10, 50, 100, and 500 μ M diltiazem in $Ca_v1.3$, $Ca_v1.3/DHPi$, and $Ca_v1.3+$. There was no significant difference in the fraction of current blocked in each of the three channel constructs at any diltiazem concentration (*one-way* ANOVA) ($n = 3-7$).

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Supplemental Figure 3. Effect of FPL 64176 on current conducted by Ca_v1.3 and Ca_v1.3+ -

A) Example traces of current through Ca_v1.3 or Ca_v1.3+ elicited with a step to 0 mV from a holding potential of -80 mV using the standard solution set. FPL 64176 at the indicated concentration was applied via extracellular perfusion as described in Materials and Methods. **B)** Example dose response experiments with Ca_v1.3+ and FPL 64176 using the NMDG-balanced solution set described in Materials and Methods. Note the increase in current amplitude at 50 and 100 nM FPL, and reduction in current amplitude at 1 μM, even though channel activation is slower than at lower concentrations.